

HIGH-CYCLE MOLDING OF CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES PIPE

Asami Nakai*¹, Tadashi Uozumi², Akio Ohtani³, Takeshi Kanamori⁴, Satoshi Nagoh⁵

¹Faculty of Engineering, Gifu University
1-1 Yanagido, Gifu, 501-1193, Japan
Email: nakai@gifu-u.ac.jp

²Composite Materials Center, Gifu University
1-1 Yanagido, Gifu, 501-1193, Japan
Email: uozumi@gifu-u.ac.jp

³Composite Materials Center, Gifu University
1-1 Yanagido, Gifu, 501-1193, Japan
Email: a_ohtani@gifu-u.ac.jp

⁴Kyoto Institute of Technology University
Matsugasaki, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto, Japan
Email: m4651005@edu.kit.ac.jp

⁵TOYOBO Co., Ltd., Shiga, Japan
Email: Satoshi_Nagoh@toyobo.jp

Keywords: Braided composites, High frequency IH, Pultrusion process, Thermoplastic composites

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to construct frame structure of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites with high impregnated intermediate materials and the high cycle molding. For the continuous straight pipe, pultrusion systems by using braiding technology with fibrous intermediate material were employed. Braided fabric was pulled in the pultrusion die having a cylindrical hole. While the resin fiber of the braided fabric was passing through the die, it melted and impregnated into reinforcing fiber. For the branched pipe joint structure, inner pressure molding by heating device of high frequency IH was adopted as high cycle molding for braided fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites. Braiding technique with two guide-rings was proposed to fabricate the braided fabric of pipe joint structure. Finally frame structure was obtained by connecting pipe joint product and cylindrical product.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are attracting a lot of attention in various area such as automobile industry and aircraft industry because of the improvement of the fuel efficiency and the capability of automobile and aircraft. Thermoplastic composite can be molded in high cycle compared to thermo-setting composite and it has also second workability and recyclability. However, the combination of continuous fiber and thermoplastic resin have disadvantage that impregnation of resin to fiber bundle is difficult since the melting viscosity of thermoplastic resin is high. Therefore, the high cycle molding with the use of high impregnated intermediate materials has been expected.

Hollow structural products with high strength and high rigidity by continuous carbon fiber are demanded as primary member for automobile industry. Frame structure as shown in Fig.1

can be constructed by welding thermoplastic composites such as cylindrical pipe, square pipe, pipe joint and so on because thermoplastic composite has second workability.

The purpose of this study is to construct frame structure with high impregnated materials by high cycle molding. For the continuous straight pipe, we have proposed one of the high-cycle-molding for c-FRTP with fibrous intermediate material and pultrusion systems by using braiding technology. Braided fabric was pulled in the pultrusion die having a cylindrical hole. While the resin fiber of the braided fabric was passing through the die, it melted and impregnated into reinforcing fiber. For the branched pipe joint structure, inner pressure molding by heating device of high frequency IH was adopted as high cycle molding for braided fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites. Braiding technique with two guide-rings was proposed to fabricate the braided fabric of pipe joint structure.

Figure 1: Schematic drawings of frame structure.

2 CONTINUOUS PULTRUSION PROCESS FOR STRAIGHT PIPE

The purpose of this study is to clarify the effects of pultrusion parameters such as selection of intermediate materials, structure of reinforcements, molding condition on the impregnation state and mechanical properties. In this paper, as an example, the effects of fiber volume fraction of commingled fiber with keeping same fiber volume fraction of molded composites were mentioned because of space limitations.

2.1 MATERIALS AND MOLDING METHOD

Fig.2 shows the braided fabric used for reinforcements. Braided fabric mainly consists of diagonally-oriented braiding yarns and middle-end-yarns (MEY) can be inserted between braiding yarns along the longitudinal direction. Since it is possible to arbitrarily set the fiber orientation angle, the mechanical properties can be designed according to the required performance.

In this study, commingled fiber was used as intermediate material made from carbon fiber (T700-12k-60E 800tex Toray industries, Inc.) as reinforcing fiber and PA66 fiber (L235-35BAU Asahi Kasei Corporation) as resin fiber. Tubular braided fabric was fabricated by using the commingled yarn, and pulled into a heated molding die. PA66 fibers were melted by heating and impregnated into the reinforcing fiber bundle, and then composite pipe was produced.

Pultrusion device is constituted by 5 equipment; mandrel having an electric heater, far infrared heater for heating the braided fabric prior to molding, molding die, cooling system and pulling device. Fig.3 shows schematic diagram of the molding die. H1 - H8 denote the electric heater which is inserted into the upper and lower molding die. Temperature of the molding die can be controlled in each heater of H1 - H8, and in this study it was set to 290, 290, 290, 290, 290, 285, 280, 275°C from the entrance side. Cooling system employs the air cooler device set at the exit of molding die. Flow rate of the air cooler was constant regardless of the pultrusion speed. Cylindrical pipe with outer diameter of 18mm and inner diameter of 15mm was molded using the molding die. Taper zone was provided at the entrance of molding die; the inner diameter was changed from 28mm to 18mm at the taper zone. The role of taper zone is to prevent backflow of melted resin and the fiber breakage due to rapid increase in molding pressure.

Figure 2: Schematic drawing of braided fabric.

Figure 3: Molding die for pultrusion molding.

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

For the measurement of the temperature history inside of the molded product during molding, a thermocouple was inserted into braided fabric. Pultrusion speed was changed as six stages of 22, 30, 70, 104, 149, 210 mm / min. In order to observe the effect of differences in molding speed on the impregnation state of the molded product, the cross section was observed by an optical microscope at the distance of 400, 600, 800, 1000 mm from the forefront of braided composite. Fig.4 shows an example of a cross-sectional photograph of the molded product with pultrusion speed of 70mm/min.

The black part of inside of fiber bundle was defined as un-impregnation area and the black part between fiber bundles was defined as the void area, respectively. Un-impregnation ratio was defined as the ratio of un-impregnated area to the cross-sectional area of each reinforcing fiber bundle and evaluated as a measure of the impregnated state. Void ratio was defined as the ratio of total area of voids to the area of cross section. Un-impregnation ratio and void ratio at four positions described above were averaged.

In order to investigate the effect of the impregnation state on the mechanical properties of the molded product, specimens were cut out into 190mm in length at the position of 600-790 mm 400-590mm from the forefront of braided composite for four-point bending test. Molding history of two specimens was the same. In order to prevent local destruction of the specimen having a pipe shape just below the indenter, a round bar of metal was inserted into the both ends of specimen. Four-point bending was performed with a supported point distance of 300mm, loading point distance of 100mm, the testing speed of 2mm/min.

Figure 4: Un-impregnation and void area.

2.3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.5 shows temperature history inside of the molded product measured by a thermocouple inserted into the braided fabric. The horizontal axis represents the distance from start point of mold to the position of temperature measurement. Essential molding distance was defined as the distance from the point where temperature reaches 260 °C, which was a melting point of PA66, to the end of the taper where pressure was applied, and essential-molding time was defined as the value obtained by dividing the pultrusion speed by the essential-molding distance. It was found that essential-molding time was decreased with the increase in the pultrusion speed.

Fig.6 shows relationships between the summation of un-impregnation and void ratios and pultrusion speed. It was found that un-impregnation ratio was increased with the increase in pultrusion speed and then became constant value of 1.5% near the 149mm/min. Void ratio was linearly increased with the increase in pultrusion speed. This reason is that essential molding time was decreased with increase in pultrusion speed.

Fig.7 shows relationships between bending strength and sum of un-impregnation and void ratios. It was found that bending strength was linearly decreased with the increase in sum of un-impregnation and void ratio. According to the slope, if the sum of un-impregnation and void ratio was increased by 5%, the bending strength was decreased by 30%.

Figure 5: Temperature history.

Figure 6: Relationships between un-impregnation and void ratio, and pultrusion speed

Figure 7: Relationships between bending strength and un-impregnation ratio.

3 HIGH CYCLE MOLDING FOR PIPE JOINT STRUCTURE

3.1 MATERIALS

Pre-impregnated tape (PT: Toyobo co. ltd) with carbon fiber and polypropylene resin was used for intermediate materials. The specifics of PT obtained by cross-section observation are shown below. PT was 5mm in length, 0.15mm in thickness, 0.4% in un-impregnation ratio, and 50% in volume fraction (Vf).

In this study, used reinforcements were braided fabrics consists of only diagonally-oriented braiding yarns. This fabric without longitudinal yarns can easily fit on the die shape and has low UCV value in inner pressure molding. UCV was defined as the proportion of un-impregnation area in fiber bundle and void between yarns to the cross section area of molding products.

The braiding machine was mainly composed of two mechanism; carrier moving mechanism and take-up mechanism. If braided fabric with pipe joint structure is fabricated, the additional process is required for the take-up mechanism and the branch part is braided by rotating the mandrel by robot arm. In case that mandrel with pipe joint structure is used, branch part of mandrel interferes with fiber bundles supplied from spindle. Therefore, the new machine for fabrication of the braided fabric with pipe joint structure has been proposed as shown in Fig.8.

New braiding machine has Guide-ring-1 and Guide-ring-2. Inside diameter of Guide-ring-1 is bigger than turning radius of mandrel. Inside diameter of Guide-ring-2 is nearly the same size as mandrel diameter. The angle between the fiber bundles supplied from spindle and axis direction of mandrel become right angle by using these guide rings, so that braided fabric with pipe joint structure can be fabricated on branch part without interference of fiber bundles supplied from spindle. In addition, braiding angle of this fabric could be controlled until the base of branch part by the Guide-ring-2.

Figure 8: New machine with guide-ring for pipe joint structure.

3.2 MOLDING METHOD

Inner pressure molding system used in this study is shown in Fig. 9. Materials with hollow structure were inserted into the molding die. The bag used in inner pressure molding was made by kapton film and PTFE tape with shape equal to inside sectional area of molding products. The bag was inserted into inside of base materials, and the die was closed. The bag was expanded by injected air, so that base material received pressure from inside. Then thermoplastic resin was melted by rapidly heated die, and the melted resin was impregnated into fiber bundle. The die was cooled by chiller device under the inner pressure.

Figure 9: Inner pressure molding system.

3.3 ESSENTIAL MOLDING TIME

Mold temperature history of the pipe joint product was measured using the thermocouple placed in the center of the die during molding as shown in Fig.9. Then essential molding time was calculated from the temperature history. Essential molding time was defined as the time in which die temperature is higher than resin melting temperature. Melting point was 170 oC, because matrix resin was polypropylene. In this study, molding temperature and time was kept at 200 oC and 5min (Heating time: 2min, Holding time: 5min). Inner pressure through the bag by air was 0.2MPa. Pipe joint products were molded by these molding conditions.

Obtained die temperature history for pipe joint product is shown in Fig. 10. According to Fig. 10, it was clarified that essential molding time was 336 sec. Cylindrical pipe could be molded when essential molding time was 150 sec in a previous study. Therefore, pipe joint product could be molded about 8 min (Heating time: 2min, Holding time: 2min, Cooling time: 3min). Finally frame structure was obtained by connecting pipe joint product and cylindrical product as shown in Fig. 11.

Figure 10 Temperature history of pipe joint product

Figure 11 Frame structure by continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites

4 CONCLUSIONS

For pultrusion using a thermoplastic resin, the essential molding time was decreased with increase in pultrusion speed, and consequently bending strength was decreased with increase in un-impregnation and void ratio according to the essential molding time. Therefore, it is considered that in order to achieve high-cycle molding using a thermoplastic resin, an increase in essential molding time is required, and it is necessary to simultaneously change the other parameters for example molding die temperature.

Braided fabric with pipe joint structure could be fabricated by proposing new braiding machine and braiding process. The fiber orientation was evaluated by the intersection point number of braiding year. Pipe joint product by use of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites could be molded at short time by inner pressure molding with heating device of high frequency IH. Finally frame structure was obtained by connecting pipe joint product and cylindrical product.